

Marketing Channels of Tapioca in Namakkal District

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Abstract:- The tapioca marketing is imperative for maximizing the profit to the farmers which enables the sellers to create the avenues for buying and selling transactions smoothly. The marketing of tapioca is significant so as a channel is required to reach the produced products to the consumers. These tapioca industries make the sago, starch and also eatables like wafer because of the increasing demand for sago, starch and other food items, the area under tapioca cultivation also increased. The tapioca production is increased for meeting out the demands of the industries and consumers therefore; the marketing channel is an effective mechanism to reach the tapioca product from farmers to final customers. In this context, the present study is an attempt to analyze the marketing channels of the tapioca products and constraints faced by the tapioca channels in the study area.

Keywords: Tapioca, Marketing, Demand, Food and Industrial Product, Channel.

I. INTRODUCTION

The tapioca cultivation and processing of food and industrial products in Namakkal District is generating economic growth and development through employment at grassroots level since tapioca serves as a basic raw material in preparing sago, starch and various other products. Thus the tapioca industries have to depend upon the tapioca cultivation for their raw material requirements. This tapioca industry enables employment opportunities to the farmers who cultivate tapioca and thus improves the agricultural economy. Similarly the tapioca cultivators have to depend upon the tapioca industries to market their cultivation of tapioca.

Besides, marketing in its broadest sense of development is the most crucial input for empowering the producers and buyers with knowledge and skills that provide them access to productive and gainful employment which enables their livelihood opportunities. Therefore, marketing is the most important delivery mechanism for enabling the regulation of the standard of tapioca crops to maximize the profits.

II. EARLIER STUDIES

➤ Srikanth (2020):

Conducted a study entitled “Factors Influencing Marketing Behaviour of Tapioca Growers” indicated that educational status, area under tapioca cultivation, experience in tapioca cultivation, mass media exposure, innovativeness, risk orientation and scientific orientation had positive and significant relationship with marketing behaviour of tapioca growers. The author further found that educational status, experience in tapioca cultivation, mass media exposure, innovativeness, risk orientation had positive and significant contribution towards marketing behaviour of tapioca growers.

➤ Vel (2019):

Study indicated that significant proportion (41%) of the respondents had medium level of overall marketing behaviour, followed by low (32%) and high (27%) levels of overall marketing behaviour. Whereas, the study is concluded that majority of the tapioca growers had medium level of marketing behaviour. Since the respondents had medium level of extension agency contact, mass media exposure and social participation, which leads for medium level of information about the market and selling and it resulted in medium level of marketing behaviour.

➤ Sakthivel (2019):

Found that concluded most of the tapioca growers had medium level of marketing behaviour. Since the respondents had medium level of extension agency contact and mass media exposure and social participation, they had only medium level of marketing behaviour.

➤ Ragavi (2019):

Study concluded that in tapioca marketing, there are three marketing channels such as Channel-I: Producer-Consumer, Channel-II: Producer- Village merchant/ Retailer Consumer, Channel-III: Producer Wholesaler/ Commission agent-Retailer/Village merchant Consumer. It is found that among the three marketing channels identified in Namakkal regulated market, the Channel-III, i.e. Producer Wholesaler-Retailer-Consumer was found more popular in marketing of tapioca.

The prices of tapioca have not influenced by the arrivals in Namakkal market. The maximum prices of tapioca were observed during the month of April. Thus, the sellers prefer these months for selling of tapioca in Namakkal market.

➤ *Subramanian (2008):*

Conducted a study on “Marketing of cassava”. The study indicated that farmers sell their tapioca products through regulated markets since they are getting more benefits in the form of higher prices and lesser marketing costs.

➤ *Objectives of the Study:*

- To study the socio-economic condition of the respondents.
- To study the marketing channels of tapioca in the study area.
- To examine the constraints faced by the respondents in tapioca marketing.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is confined to Namakkal District. For the selection of 50 samples, the researchers have used the purposive random sampling method with replacement adopted in the study.

➤ *Socio-Economic Profile:*

- *Gender wise classification:*

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents According to their Gender

S. No	Particulars	Number	Percent
1	Male	38	76.00
2	Female	12	24.00
Total		50	100.0

The study findings reveals that the data presented in Table.1 shows that the majority [76%] of the respondents are male, followed by the female [24%].

- *Age Wise Classification:*

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents According to their Age

S. No	Particulars	Number	Percent
1	Below 25 years	07	14.00
2	Between 25-30	13	26.00
3	Between 31-50	13	26.00
4	Above 50	17	34.00
Total		50	100.0

Table.2 shows that a considerable portion [34%] of respondents is belonged to the age group of above 50 years category. It is noticed that a considerable level [26%] of respondents are belonged to the age group of 25-30 years category, followed by 26 percent of the respondents are belonged to the age group of between 31-45 years category. Only a few [07%] of the respondents are belonged to the age category of less than 25 years in the study area.

- *Educational Status:*

Table 3 Distribution of Respondents According to Education Status

S. No	Particulars	Number	Percent
1	Illiterate	02	04.00
2	Primary	07	14.00
3	Secondary	06	12.00
4	High School	12	24.00
5	Higher Secondary	14	28.00
6	UG and PG	09	18.00
Total		50	100.0

Table 3 indicates that a considerable level [28%] of the respondents found to be higher secondary, followed by [24%] high school. It noticed that a small portion [18%] of the respondents is studied upto under and post graduates, followed by [14%] primary schooling and [12%] secondary schooling. Only a few [4%] found as illiterate in marketing of tapioca process.

• *Monthly Income Status:*

Table 4 Distribution of Respondents According to Monthly Income Status

S. No	Particulars	Number	Percent
1	Below Rs. 25,000	14	28.00
2	Between Rs. 25,000-50,000	19	38.00
3	Above Rs. 50,000	17	34.00
Total		50	100.0

Table 4 finds that a considerable proportion [38%] of the respondents are earned their monthly income between Rs. 25,000-50,000, followed by [34%] are earned above Rs.50,000 as monthly income and [28%] of the respondents are earned below Rs.25,000.

• *Tapioca Marketing Channels:*

Table 5 Distribution of Respondents According to Marketing Channels

S. No	Particulars	Number	Percent
1	Channel-I: Producer- Consumer	10	20.00
2	Channel-II: Producer- Village merchant/ Retailer Consumer	14	28.00
3	Channel-III: Producer - Wholesaler/ Commission agent-Retailer/ Village merchant Consumer	26	34.00
Total		50	100.0

Note: $\chi^2 = 0.169$ significant at 0.0123

Fig 1 Distribution of Respondents According to Marketing Channels

The available data in Table 5 shows that a considerable level [34%] of the respondents is sold their tapioca products to the Channel-III: Producer - Wholesaler/ Commission agent-Retailer/ Village merchant Consumer, followed by [28%] Channel-II: Producer- Village merchant/ Retailer Consumer. It is noticed that 20 per cent of the respondents are sold their tapioca products on direct mode to the consumers [Channel-I: Producer- Consumer]. The chi-square test result [$\chi^2 = 0.169$ significant at 0.0123] highly associated with tapioca of marketing channels. The study is implied that most of the tapioca farmers are selling their products in the marketing with the supports of middle men in the study area.

• *Marketing Area:*

Table 6 Distribution of Respondents According to Marketing Area

S. No	Particulars	Number	Percent
1	Local Level	16	32.00
2	District Level	14	28.00
3	State Level	12	24.00
4	National level	08	16.00
Total		50	100.0

Note: $\chi^2 = 1.052$ significant at 0.025

Table 6 reveals that a considerable level [32%] of the respondents is sold their tapioca products at local markets, followed by [28%] district level and [24%] state level. Further, the study is found that 16 per cent of the respondents have sold their tapioca products in national level. The chi-square test result [$\chi^2 = 1.052$ significant at 0.025] of market area has highly associated with tapioca sales. Hence, the study is concluded that most of the farmers of tapioca are selling their products within the state since tapioca demand is rising up and also for better profits.

- *Tapioca product Price Fixation for Marketing:*

Table 7 Distribution of Respondents According to the Price Fixation

S. No	Particulars	Number	Percent
1	Based on quality	25	50.00
2	Based on quantity	10	20.00
3	Demand from wholesalers	09	18.00
4	Demand during festival season	06	12.00
Total		50	100.0

Note: $\chi^2 = 1.372$ significant at 0.023

Fig 2 Distribution of Respondents According to the Price Fixation of Tapioca

The available data [in Table.7] reveals that half [50%] of the respondents are fixed their tapioca products price on the basis of quality, followed by [20%] quantity. It is understood that 18 per cent of the respondents are fixed the price for the tapioca on the basis of demands have made by the wholesalers and [12%] demands of festival seasons.

The chi-square test result [$\chi^2 = 1.372$ significant at 0.023] is corroborated that the price fixations is high associated with tapioca sales in the study area. Hence, the study is confined that most of tapioca farmers are found to be profitable since it is fixed on the basis of its quality and quantity during the sales of the products.

- *Constraints of Respondents in Tapioca Marketing:*

Table 8 Distribution of Respondents According to their Problems in Marketing of Tapioca [Multiple Responses]

S. No	Particulars	Eigen Ranking	Percent
1	Delay in payment	I	90.00
2	Problem in fixing price	II	88.00
3	Fluctuation in demand	III	85.00
4	Transport cost	IV	77.00
5	High Competition	V	71.00

Table 8 provides the Eigen ranking system results that the majority [90%] of the respondents expressed that payment delay is the significant cause of tapioca marketing; followed by [88%] fixing of the price of tapioca products and [85%] fluctuation in demand is becoming unpredictable problem in tapioca sells in the study area. It is noted that transport cost is a constraint in marketing of tapioca products; it is reported by 77 per cent of the respondents and [71%] high competition in the tapioca marketing in the study area.

IV. MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

➤ *Socio-Economic Profile Of The Respondents:*

- The study found that the majority [76%] of the respondents are male, followed by the female [24%].
- The study indicated that considerable portion [34%] of respondents is belonged to the age group of above 50 years category. It is noticed that a considerable level [26%] of respondents are belonged to the age group of 25-30 years category, followed by 26 percent of the respondents are belonged to the age group of between 31-45 years category. Only a few [07%] of the respondents are belonged to the age category of less than 25 years in the study area.
- The study revealed that considerable level [28%] of the respondents found to be higher secondary, followed by [24%] high school.
- It noticed that a small portion [18%] of the respondents is studied upto under and post graduates, followed by [14%] primary schooling and [12%] secondary schooling. Only a few [4%] found as illiterate in marketing of tapioca process.
- It is understood that 38 percent of the respondents are earned their monthly income between Rs. 25,000-50,000, followed by [34%] are earned above Rs.50,000 as monthly income and [28%] of the respondents are earned below Rs.25,000.

➤ *Tapioca Marketing Channels:*

- The study findings highlighted that considerable level [34%] of the respondents is sold their tapioca products to the Channel-III: Producer - Wholesaler/ Commission agent-Retailer/ Village merchant Consumer, followed by [28%] Channel-II: Producer- Village merchant/ Retailer Consumer.
- It is noticed that 20 per cent of the respondents are sold their tapioca products on direct mode to the consumers [Channel-I: Producer- Consumer]. The chi-square test result [$\chi^2 = 0.169$ significant at 0.0123] highly associated with tapioca of marketing channels. Therefore, the study is implied that most of the tapioca farmers are selling their products in the marketing with the supports of middle men in the study area.

➤ *Marketing Area:*

- The study indicated that considerable level [32%] of the respondents is sold their tapioca products at local markets, followed by [28%] district level and [24%] state level. Further, the study is found that 16 per cent of the respondents have sold their tapioca products in national level.
- The chi-square test result [$\chi^2 = 1.052$ significant at 0.025] of market area has highly associated with tapioca sales. Hence, the study is concluded that most of the farmers of tapioca are selling their products within the state since tapioca demand is rising up and also for better profits.

➤ *Tapioca product Price Fixation for Marketing:*

- The study revealed that half [50%] of the respondents are fixed their tapioca products price on the basis of quality, followed by [20%] quantity. It is understood that 18 per cent of the respondents are fixed the price for the tapioca on the basis of demands have made by the wholesalers and [12%] demands of festival seasons.
- The chi-square test result [$\chi^2 = 1.372$ significant at 0.023] is corroborated that the price fixations is high associated with tapioca sales in the study area. Hence, the study is confined that most of tapioca farmers are found to be profitable since its fixed on the basis of its quality and quantity during the sales of the products.

➤ *Constraints of Respondents in Tapioca Marketing:*

- The study found that majority [90%] of the respondents expressed that payment delay is the significant cause of tapioca marketing; followed by [88%] fixing of the price of tapioca products and [85%] fluctuation in demand is becoming unpredictable problem in tapioca sells in the study area.
- It is noted that transport cost is a constraint in marketing of tapioca products; it is reported by 77 per cent of the respondents and [71%] high competition in the tapioca marketing in the study area.

V. CONCLUSION

In the emerging business settings, tapioca product marketing is needed a channel to reach its products to the customer/ consumer. The present is concluded that most of the tapioca cultivators are preferred to market their produce to the Channel-II [Producer-Village merchant/ Retailer Consumer] and Channel-III [Producer-Wholesaler/ Commission agent-Retailer/Village merchant Consumer] for maximum profits on reduction of transport cost and other related costs [labour wage] cost since all the cost are bearing by the middle men when the tapioca selling through marketing channels of II and III. Moreover, the middle men have made all the arrangement to take all the responsibilities to mobility of the tapioca products from the tapioca cultivation field so as tapioca farmers are willing to sell their products to the agents, contractors, retailers and wholesaler.

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